

Research

Correlation of Glycated Hemoglobin and Testosterone in Chinese men of Henan Province with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

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Abstract : In majority of the cases of diabetes the severe and persistent complications contribute to different ailments and even demise. Since the prevalence of diabetes is steadily rising throughout the age range, one-third of type 2 diabetes patients are found to have low levels of testosterone. As glycated hemoglobin acts as a biomarker for the assessment of control and severity of diabetes we focused on determining the correlation between testosterone and glycated hemoglobin in Chinese patients with type 2 diabetes and also to analyze the association between testosterone and glycated hemoglobin in type 2 diabetic, prediabetic patients and control group.

Research Design and Method: The testosterone-glycated hemoglobin association was studied in 156 type 2 Diabetes patients, 159 Prediabetes patients and 180 healthy men. In addition to the aforementioned correlation, the association of SHBG and Free testosterone to other factors such as age, BMI, lipid profile, and HbA1c was also analyzed in 3 participant classes. **Result :** Mean concentration of testosterone in T2DM patients 5.5 ± 2.2 ng/ml is low than Control (6.47 ± 1.4 ng/ml) and Prediabetic group (6.2 ± 2.3 ng/ml) with a P value of less than 0.001 and 0.002 respectively. Free testosterone levels were significantly lower in T2DM patients (11.8 ± 5.9 pg/ml) and prediabetic patients (12.6 ± 5.3 pg/ml) than control group (15.5 ± 3.4 pg/ml) with a P value of less than 0.001 for both. In T2DM patients there was an inverse correlation between testosterone and HbA1c ($r = -0.268$, $P = 0.001$), BMI ($r = -0.29$, $P < 0.001$), TC ($r = -0.211$, $P = 0.008$), TG ($r = -0.33$, $P = 0.001$) and positive association with HDL ($r = 0.231$, $P = 0.004$); SHBG correlated positively with age ($r = 0.475$, $P < 0.001$), HDL ($r = 0.191$, $P = 0.01$) and negatively with BMI ($r = -0.392$, $P < 0.001$), TG ($r = -0.453$, $P < 0.001$), TC ($r = -0.258$, $P = 0.001$) and HbA1c ($r = -0.207$, $P = 0.009$). Free testosterone correlated negatively with age in all 3 groups of participants. The negative association between testosterone and Glycated

hemoglobin persisted even after adjusting for age and BMI. In multiple regression analysis, BMI and HbA1c were identified as independent variables for Testosterone. **Conclusion:** A significant inverse association between Glycated hemoglobin and testosterone in patients with type 2 diabetes was observed. As HbA1c indicates the glycemic control of past 3 months in type 2 diabetes patient with high level of Glycated hemoglobin is an indicator to check the testosterone level along with other routine tests for determining presence of asymptomatic and dormant complications.

Keywords: Type 2 Diabetes, Prediabetes, Testosterone, Glycated hemoglobin, SHBG, Free testosterone.

Introduction:

Over the past three decades the prevalence of Diabetes in China has strongly increased. According to the most recent report in the International Diabetes Federation Diabetes Atlas, the general pervasiveness of diabetes is 9.1% in adults, inferring that 415 million people experience diabetes all around. Besides, impaired glucose regulation has been reported in 318 million adults and are at a high risk for having diabetes. China positions number one, with the most elevated number of individuals with diabetes. (1)

There is ample evidence to show that patients with type 2 diabetes (T2D) tend to develop numerous complications, including hypogonadism. Type 2 diabetic men with low testosterone levels have additionally been found to have a high predominance of manifestations reminiscent of hypogonadism, for example, fatigability and erectile dysfunction. Furthermore, numerous examinations have demonstrated that the testosterone levels in men with diabetes were lower than those of the nondiabetic ones. Since the prevalence of diabetes is steadily rising throughout the age range, one-third of type 2 diabetes patients are found to have low levels of testosterone leads to potential infertility and decreased sexual function resulting in a public health burden. In perspective on the opposite connection among BMI and testosterone fixations in both type 1 and type 2 diabetes, Hypogonadism is presumably identified with insulin resistance (2). Sex hormone binding globulin (SHBG) has risen as one of the numerous hereditary and environmental elements that possibly add to the pathophysiology of Type 2 diabetes mellitus. In men, 40% of serum testosterone is firmly bound to SHBG, 58% freely to albumin, and the staying 0.5–2% flows as the free structure. SHBG isn't only a latent bearer, however effectively controls the cellular uptake of testosterone. (3)

Glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) is used as a diagnostic test for diabetes mellitus and reflects the glycemic control in diabetic patients for last 3 months. In diabetes, higher measures of glycated hemoglobin, demonstrating more unfortunate control of blood glucose levels, have been related with nephropathy, neuropathy, and retinopathy, cardiovascular disease. A survey of the UKPDS, Action to Control Cardiovascular Risk in Diabetes (ACCORD), ADVANCE and Veterans Affairs Diabetes Trials (VADT) evaluated that the dangers of the major and minor complications of diabetes such as, diabetic retinopathy, diabetic nephropathy, diabetic neuropathy, and macrovascular diseases diminished by about 3% for each 1 mmol/mol decline in HbA1c.(4)

Studies revealed that one third of men with type 2 diabetes have low testosterone level. Our aim is to evaluate the relationship between testosterone and Glycated hemoglobin in Chinese patients having type 2 diabetes and also compare the testosterone-HbA1c association in prediabetic, type 2 diabetic patients and control group.

Research Design and method:

The study included 156 T2DM and 159 prediabetic patients and 180 healthy men from the department of Endocrinology of 1st affiliated hospital of Zhengzhou University, Henan province, China. Correlation with serum testosterone and Glycated hemoglobin was analyzed. In addition to serum testosterone levels, SHBG and Free Testosterone levels were also collected to observe their correlation with age, BMI, Blood pressure, lipid profile and HbA1c.

The clinical and biochemical data were analyzed retrospectively. Blood pressure was measured while the subject was in a sitting position using a validated automated blood pressure machine. Blood samples for testosterone, SHBG, cholesterol, triglyceride, Low density lipoprotein (LDL), High density lipoprotein (LDL), HbA1c were collected in a stable state in the morning. Glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) levels were measured using a high-performance liquid chromatography method. The serum total cholesterol, Triglyceride, LDL cholesterol, HDL cholesterol concentrations were measured using enzymatic methods. Serum testosterone concentrations were measured by the liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry, SHBG was measured by immunofluometric assay and free testosterone by equilibrium dialysis. These patients did not have hematological disorder, hypothyroidism, hypogonadism and did not receive any steroid medication.

Type 2 diabetes was diagnosed according to the guideline, either the fasting plasma glucose (FPG) ≥ 7.0 mmol/l or the 2- h plasma glucose (2- h PG) value after a 75- g oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) ≥ 11.1 or Typical symptoms of diabetes (polydipsia, polyuria, polyphagia and weight loss) plus random blood glucose level ≥ 11.1 . HbA1c $\geq 6.5\%$ is used as a reference in diagnosing diabetes. Prediabetes was diagnosed using two specific parameters, impaired fasting glucose (IFG) defined as fasting plasma glucose (FPG) of 6.1-6.9 mmol/L (110 to 125 mg/dL) and impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) defined as 2 h plasma glucose of 7.8-11.0 mmol/L (140-200 mg/dL) after ingestion of 75 g of oral glucose intake. Reference values for other variables were as follows: Testosterone 1.42-9.23 ng/ml, SHBG 10-89 nmol/l, Free testosterone 8.69-54.69pg/ml, Total cholesterol < 5.2 mmol/l, TG < 1.7 mmol/l, HDL-C > 0.91 mmol/l, LDL-C 3.61 mmol/l.

Statistical Analysis:

SPSS 23.0 version was used for statistical analysis. Clinical and biochemical data were presented as Mean $\pm$ SD. One-way ANOVA or Kruskal Wallis test were used to analyze statistically significant differences between groups. Analysis of correlation between serum Testosterone, SHBG, Free Testosterone and age, BMI, blood pressure, Lipid profile, HbA1c was conducted in T2DM, Prediabetes and Control group using Pearson's correlation analysis or Spearman's analysis. Simple linear regression was performed to identify predictor variables for Testosterone, SHBG and Free Testosterone. Multiple regression analysis were performed to analyze their combined effect on Testosterone, SHBG and Free testosterone. T2DM patients were further divided into quartile groups according to HbA1c level and mean difference of Testosterone was analyzed using One-way ANOVA. *P* value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results:

Clinical and biochemical characteristics of 156 Type 2 diabetic patients, 159 Prediabetic patients and 180 healthy men are shown in Table 1 with statistical significance of difference. The mean value of testosterone in T2DM patients 5.5 ± 2.2 ng/ml is significantly lower than Control (6.47 ± 1.4 ng/ml) and Prediabetic group (6.2 ± 2.3 ng/ml) with a *P* value of less than 0.001 for control group and 0.002 for prediabetic group. Free testosterone is also significantly low in T2DM patients 11.8 ± 5.9 pg/ml Prediabetic group 12.6 ± 5.3 pg/ml than control group

15.5 ± 3.4 pg/ml and with a *P* value of less than 0.001 for both. SHBG level was comparatively high in both T2DM patients (38.7±27.5 nmol/L) and Prediabetic patients (35.3±17.8 nmol/L) than the control group (32.9±10.4) but this difference was not significant. HbA1c was significantly high in T2DM patients (7.3±1.8%) than Prediabetic (5.9±0.5%, *P*<0.001) and normal group (5.4±0.03, *P*<0.001). BMI, SBP, TG, TC, LDL were significantly elevated in T2DM and prediabetic patients than the control group.

Correlation between Testosterone, SHBG, Free Testosterone and other variables in 3 groups of people are shown in Table 2. In T2DM patients Testosterone correlated negatively with HbA1c, BMI, TC, TG and positively with HDL; SHBG correlated positively with age, HDL and negatively with BMI, DBP, TG, TC and HbA1c. In Prediabetic patients Testosterone correlated positively with age, HDL and negatively with BMI and TG; SHBG has positive correlation with age, HDL and negative correlation with BMI and TG. Free Testosterone correlated negatively with age in all 3 groups of patients. There was a significant positive correlation of HbA1c with both SHBG(*r*= 0.196, *P*<0.001) in the control group. The significant negative correlation between HbA1c and Testosterone was only present in T2DM patients; other 2 groups had such no correlation. After adjusting for age, BMI the correlation between HbA1c and Testosterone in T2DM patients persisted (*r*= -0.212, *P*=0.008) in T2DM patients. Simple linear regression identified BMI, TG, HDL, HbA1c as predictor variables for Testosterone in T2DM patients; age, BMI, HDL, TG in Prediabetic patients and BMI, HDL, TG in healthy group. Multiple stepwise regression (Table: 3) showed BMI and HbA1c as predictor variable of Testosterone, for each unit increase of BMI and HbA1c Testosterone level is expected to decrease 0.25 ng/ml in T2DM patients. BMI, TG, TC in Prediabetic patients and HDL, age, TG in control group were identified as independent variable for Testosterone in Multiple regression analysis. HbA1c was not identified as predictor for SHBG and FT in neither T2DM nor Prediabetes patients. Age, BMI, TC, HDL, SBP were independent determinant for SHBG in T2DM patients and age, BMI, TG predictor variable for SHBG in Prediabetes patients (Table: 4). In all 3 groups age was a predictor variable for Free testosterone.

The T2DM patients were further divided into 4 groups according to the quartile range of HbA1c and the mean was compared using One-way ANOVA. Results showed the mean of Testosterone (4.8±1.8 ng/ml) in 4th quartile range of HbA1c (8.2-13.9%) is significantly lower (*P*=0.003) than

the mean of testosterone (6.2±2.5 ng/ml) in 1st quartile range of HbA1c (4.7-5.8%) illustrated in Figure:3.

Table 1: Clinical characteristics of T2DM, Prediabetes and Control group.

	T2DM	Prediabetes	Control	P
Age(years)	54.6±13.5	51.5±15.3	37.31±14.28	a<0.001 b<0.001 c=0.05
BMI (kg/m²)	26.34±3.25	26.26±3.48	24.85±4.22	a<0.001 b<0.001 c=0.8
Systolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)	138.1±20.1	137.9±18.6	130.9±16.7	a<0.001 b<0.001 c=0.94
Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg)	81.9±11.9	83.7±12.1	80.1±12.9	a=0.156 b=0.005 c=0.174
Total Cholesterol (mmol/L)	4.89±1.24	5±1.03	4.5±0.97	a<0.001 b<0.001 c=0.249
Triglyceride (mmol/L)	2.1±1.8	1.8±1.3	1.6±1.2	a<0.001 b=0.001 c=0.717
LDL (mmol/L)	3.1±0.8	3.2±0.9	2.78±0.83	a<0.001 b<0.001 c=0.25
HDL (mmol/L)	1.2±0.3	1.2±3.5	1.29±0.28	a<0.001 b=0.2 c=0.017
HbA1c(%)	7.3±1.8	5.9±0.5	5.4±0.3	a<0.001 b<0.001 c<0.001
Testosterone (ng/ml)	5.5±2.2	6.2±2.3	6.47±1.4	a<0.001 b=0.194 c=0.002
SHBG(nmol/L)	38.7±27.5	35.3±17.8	32.9±10.4	0.6
Free Testosterone (pg/ml)	11.8±5.9	12.6±5.3	15.5±3.4	a<0.001 b<0.001 c=0.07
Total no. of patients	156	159	180	

a = Difference between T2DM and Control group
b = Difference between Prediabetes and Control group
c = Difference between T2DM and Prediabetes group.

Table 2: Correlation analysis of Testosterone, SHBG and Free testosterone with other variables in 3 groups.

Variable		Testosterone		SHBG		Free Testosterone	
		r	P	r	P	r	P
Age	T2DM	0.061 ^a	0.446	0.475	<0.001	-0.345	<0.001
	Prediabetes	0.178	0.03	0.419	<0.001	-0.247	0.002
	Control	-0.194	0.009	0.459	<0.001	-0.267	<0.001
BMI	T2DM	-0.29	<0.001	-0.392	<0.001	0.045	0.55
	Prediabetes	-0.378	<0.001	-0.238	0.003	-0.088	0.27
	Control	-0.28	<0.001	-0.003	0.967	-0.068	0.364
SBP	T2DM	0.042	0.59	0.05	0.49	-0.017	0.83
	Prediabetes	0.089	0.262	0.156	0.05	-0.108	0.17
	Control	-0.04	0.56	0.104	0.165	0.04	0.561
DBP	T2DM	-0.141	0.179	-0.252	0.001	0.023	0.77
	Prediabetes	-0.038	0.639	-0.072	0.36	0.043	0.58
	Control	-0.039	0.604	-0.053	0.476	0.016	0.83
TC	T2DM	-0.211	0.008	-0.258	0.001	0.131	0.1
	Prediabetes	0.083	0.295	0.07	0.38	0.094	0.24
	Control	0.036	0.632	0.246	0.001	0.038	0.61
TG	T2DM	-0.33	<0.001	-0.453	<0.001	0.134	0.095
	Prediabetes	-0.336	<0.001	-0.276	<0.001	0.04	0.61
	Control	-0.177	0.018	0.08	0.28	-0.064	0.39
HDL	T2DM	0.231	0.004	0.191	0.01	0.028	0.73
	Prediabetes	0.376	<0.001	0.263	<0.001	0.065	0.415
	Control	0.331	<0.001	0.212	0.004	0.04	0.57
LDL	T2DM	-0.151	0.059	-0.208	0.009	0.029	0.72
	Prediabetes	0.036	0.65	0.04	0.57	0.004	0.96
	Control	-0.085	0.254	0.142	0.058	-0.026	0.725
HbA1c	T2DM	-0.268	0.001	-0.207	0.009	-0.054	0.507
	Prediabetes	-0.097	0.23	0.046	0.56	0.003	0.96
	Control	-0.131	0.08	0.176	0.018	0.021	0.78

Table 3: Multiple regression analysis for Testosterone T2DM, Prediabetes and Control groups.

Group	Model	Predictor	B	SE	Beta	t	Adjusted R ²	P
T2DM								
	1	(Constant)	10.56	1.353		7.805		<0.001
		BMI	-0.192	0.051	-0.29	-3.761	0.078	<0.001
	2	(Constant)	11.939	1.422		8.397		<0.001
		BMI	-0.175	0.05	-0.264	-3.47		0.001
		HbA1c	-0.251	0.093	-0.205	-2.691	0.114	0.008
Prediabetes								
	1	(Constant)	12.859	1.314		9.783		<0.001
		BMI	-0.254	0.05	-0.378	-5.114	0.137	<0.001
	2	(Constant)	9.731	1.684		5.779		<0.001
		BMI	-0.205	0.051	-0.305	-3.982		<0.001
		HDL	1.438	0.5	0.22	2.875	0.167	0.012
Control								
	1	(Constant)	4.412	0.452		9.768		<0.001
		HDL	1.596	0.342	0.331	4.672	0.1	<0.001
	2	(Constant)	5.099	0.511		9.988		<0.001
		HDL	1.584	0.336	0.328	4.717		<0.001
		Age	-0.018	0.007	-0.189	-2.721	0.135	0.007
	3	(Constant)	4.657	0.547		8.522		<0.001
		HDL	1.793	0.347	0.371	5.172		<0.001
		Age	-0.02	0.007	-0.215	-3.073		0.002
		TG	0.169	0.08	0.155	2.128	0.152	0.035

Table 4: Multiple regression analysis for SHBG in T2DM, Prediabetes and Control Group.

Group	Model	Predictor	B	SE	Beta	t	Adjusted R ²	P
T2DM								
	1	(Constant)	122.443	16.711		7.327		<0.001
		BMI	-3.181	0.63	-0.377	-5.051	0.137	<0.001
	2	(Constant)	88.297	19.419		4.547		<0.001
		BMI	-2.871	0.619	-0.34	-4.636		<0.001
		Age	0.475	0.148	0.235	3.203	0.186	0.002
	3	(Constant)	103.665	19.708		5.26		<0.001
		BMI	-2.541	0.616	-0.301	-4.127		<0.001
		Age	0.449	0.145	0.222	3.088		0.002
		TC	-4.621	1.604	-0.209	-2.881	0.223	0.005

Group	Model	Predictor	B	SE	Beta	t	Adjusted R ²	P	
	4	(Constant)	60.502	23.613		2.562		0.011	
		BMI	-1.729	0.653	-0.205	-2.649		0.009	
		Age	0.435	0.141	0.215	3.076		0.002	
		TC	-5.772	1.603	-0.26	-3.602		<0.001	
		HDL	23.991	7.669	0.238	3.128	0.265	0.002	
	5	(Constant)	46.325	24.394		1.899		0.059	
		BMI	-2.03	0.663	-0.241	-3.062		0.003	
		Age	0.364	0.144	0.18	2.525		0.013	
		TC	-5.853	1.587	-0.264	-3.689		<0.001	
		HDL	23.01	7.607	0.228	3.025		0.003	
		SBP	0.199	0.098	0.146	2.029	0.28	0.044	
Prediabetes									
	1	(Constant)	10.288	4.514		2.279		0.024	
		Age	0.486	0.084	0.419	5.789	0.171	<0.001	
	2	(Constant)	40.132	10.631		3.775		<0.001	
		Age	0.474	0.082	0.409	5.785		<0.001	
	3	BMI	-1.112	0.361	-0.218	-3.083	0.213	0.002	
		(Constant)	40.838	10.529		3.879		<0.001	
		Age	0.455	0.082	0.392	5.571		<0.001	
		3	BMI	-0.964	0.364	-0.189	-2.645		0.009
			TG	-1.957	0.956	-0.147	-2.047	0.229	0.042
Control									
	1	(Constant)	20.402	1.942		10.503		<0.001	
		Age	0.335	0.049	0.459	6.892	0.206	<0.001	
	2	(Constant)	9.8	3.655		2.682		0.008	
		Age	0.337	0.047	0.462	7.138		<0.001	
		HDL	8.143	2.403	0.219	3.388	0.25	0.001	

Figure 1: Bar chart showing mean value of Testosterone, SHBG, Free testosterone in Type 2 diabetes, Prediabetes and control group.

Figure 2: Correlation between Testosterone and HbA1c in T2DM patients

Figure 3 : Testosterone levels in quartile groups of HbA1c in T2DM patients.

3. Discussion:

Type 2 diabetes leads to several complications in the body. Beyond the microvascular and macrovascular complication Diabetes leads to hypogonadism, cancer, liver disease etc. These additional complications also hamper the quality of life.

This study reveals that serum testosterone levels is lower in Type 2 Diabetes patients than Prediabetes patients and normal healthy men. Testosterone is inversely associated with Glycated hemoglobin in type 2 diabetes patients. A lower level of Testosterone was found in diabetic patients with high levels of HbA1c. Several studies reported that Testosterone level are low in patients with diabetes and majority of patients are more yielded to develop hypogonadism. There was a large population based study which reported that testosterone can predict the value of Glycated hemoglobin in diabetic patients(5). Our study did not have patients with hypogonadism and aimed at observing whether Glycated hemoglobin could predict the testosterone levels. In this study there was a linear negative association between HbA1c and testosterone and Multiple regression analysis also found both HbA1c and BMI as a determinant of Testosterone. The multiple comparison in quartile groups of Glycated hemoglobin in type 2 diabetes revealed that patients with higher level of Glycated hemoglobin has low levels of testosterone. Previous studies reported that testosterone can affect the HbA1c as it is a stimulating factor for erythropoiesis and this study showed a negative association between them where high level of HbA1c can result in low testosterone. (6,7)

Studies suggest that low Testosterone increases insulin resistance and testosterone therapy improves the insulin resistance by increasing the muscle mass and decreasing fat mass(8). The impact of BMI on hypogonadism in type 2 diabetic men can be clarified by the conversion of testosterone into estrogen by aromatase results in decline in the testosterone levels.(9) Testosterone level in type 2 diabetes patients was negatively correlated with BMI which is compatible with established findings. Testosterone was also found to have an inverse relation with triglyceride and total cholesterol and a positive correlation with HDL-C which is congruent with the reports of risk factor for cardiovascular disease in diabetes patients with low testosterone level. (10)

In our study all 3 groups' participants' Testosterone correlated negatively with BMI and Triglyceride. This is explained by the hypogonadal obesity cycle where low testosterone and

dyslipidaemia are interrelated and insulin resistance leads to decreased leydig cell function which further causes low testosterone level. (11)

Insulin inversely affects SHBG production by the liver (12). In this study SHBG showed a negative correlation with HbA1c in type 2 diabetic patients and a positive correlation in control group but no significant correlation were found in Prediabetes patients. In Type 2 diabetes patients and Prediabetes patients SHBG positively correlated with age and negatively correlated with BMI which is consistent with previous established study where obesity was identified as a determinant of low SHBG (13). In multiple regression analysis HbA1c was not identified as a predictor for SHBG level in type 2 diabetes patients. In previous reports SHBG was positively correlated with HDL-C and negatively correlated with Total cholesterol and triglyceride in healthy young men (14). The positive association of SHBG-HDL is equivalent in this study of patients with Diabetes and Prediabetes and control group but the negative correlation of SHBG with TG an TC is only seen in diabetic group rather than the control group. In addition there was also a negative correlation between SHBG and LDL-C and Total cholesterol in diabetic patients. In multiple regression analysis total cholesterol and HDL-C were determined as predictors of SHBG along with BMI.

There is a significant difference in mean value of free testosterone in 3 groups of participants. Type 2 diabetes patients have lower level of free testosterone than Prediabetes patients and control group. A report regarding importance of calculated free testosterone revealed that elderly men with borderline testosterone and altered SHBG concentration can be evaluated for hypogonadism by calculated free testosterone (15). In our study there is inverse correlation between free testosterone and age and no other factors were associated with free testosterone. Low free testosterone is inversely associated with insulin resistance (16) but there is no association with Glycated hemoglobin.

Testosterone production is influenced by leydig cell function of HPG axis. T2DM patients have increased level of pro inflammatory cytokines, this along with increased insulin and leptin inhibit the HPG axis at different levels(17). Pro-inflammatory cytokines as proposed by Hong et. Al (18) Tumor necrosis factor α and interleukins 6 inhibits the GnRH production from hypothalamus and eventually decreased LH and FSH production result in impaired gonadal

stimulation and function. Leptin levels are negatively correlated with testosterone production. Insulin resistance impairs Leydig cell function as leptin is correlated with insulin resistance and leptin receptors expression on rat Leydig cell showed decreased testosterone production.

There are several studies evaluating the association of hypogonadism and Diabetes as well as low testosterone and insulin resistance. Testosterone therapy showed improvement of diabetes and HbA1c level but the underlying mechanism for this negative association between HbA1c and Testosterone is yet to be determined.

4. Conclusion:

A significant inverse association between Glycated haemoglobin and testosterone in patients with type 2 diabetes was observed. As HbA1c indicates the glycemic control of past 3 months in type 2 diabetes patient with high level of Glycated hemoglobin is an indicator to check the testosterone level along with other routine tests for determining presence of asymptomatic and dormant complications.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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